

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_natural_a_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:55:38 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	33.53	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.5116	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...x_natural_a_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:55:38 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	11.56	μm	
Min:	-5.804	μm	
Max:	5.757	μm	
Size:	225967	digits	
Spacing:	0.05116	nm	
NM-points ratio:	11.67 % (1050430 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 11:55:38 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	11.56	μm	
Size:	225967	digits	
Spacing:	0.05116	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	2.032	μm	
Ssk	-0.2049		
Sku	2.629		
Sp	5.751	μm	
Sv	5.810	μm	
Sz	11.56	μm	
Sa	1.642	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.3053	%	
Smc	2.572	μm	
Sxp	4.268	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	27.44	μm	
Str	0.7947		
Std	50.74	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.3808		
Sdr	6.215	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.07688	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	2.649	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.07688	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	1.958	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	2.410	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2383	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

- ISO 25178 8.
- Furrow 9.
- Texture direction 10.
- Texture isotropy 11.
- SSFA 12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	5.872	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.777	µm
Mean density of furrows	3313	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	90.01	°
Second direction	0.03081	°
Third direction	135.0	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	85.33	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

